

Table S1. Compaction index with different additive dosages.

Formulation	Optimum water content (%)	Maximum dry density (g/cm ³)
Untreated	20.4	1.68
B2	21.0	1.46
B5	21.5	1.28
B8	21.7	1.14
B5C0	21.5	1.28
B5C0.2	21.7	1.19
B5C0.5	21.8	1.12
B5C1	22.5	1.12
B5C2	23.2	1.02

Table S2. Calculation details for the upper bound analysis of abiotic carbonation.

Parameter	Value	Source
Atmospheric CO ₂	420 ppm (42 Pa)	Current global average
Curing temperature	22 ± 2°C (295 K)	Experimental condition
Assumed headspace volume	100 mL (generous upper bound)	Plastic-wrapped specimen
Moles of CO ₂ in headspace	1.7 × 10 ⁻⁶ mol	$n = PV/RT$
Max CaCO ₃ from headspace CO ₂	0.17 mg	1:1 molar ratio, $M = 100$ g/mol
Specimen volume	~196 cm ³	$\pi \times 2.5^2 \times 10$ cm
Specimen dry mass	~330 g	196 cm ³ × 1.68 g/cm ³
Max abiotic carbonate fraction	~5 × 10 ⁻⁵ %	0.17 mg/330 g
Measured carbonate fraction	1.5-4.3%	Present study
Ratio (measured/abiotic max)	~30000-86000 times	Four orders of magnitude
Urea half-life at 25°C (no urease)	~3.6 years	Callahan et al. 2005
Urea decomposed in 28d (no urease)	<0.02%	First-order decay
Concrete carbonation rate (upper bound)	1-5 mm/year	Papadakis et al. 1991
Max carbonation depth in 28d	<0.4 mm	5 mm/yr × 28/365
Affected cross-section fraction	<1.6%	0.4 mm/25 mm radius
Max abiotic CaCO ₃ via atmospheric CO ₂ diffusion	<0.05% (specimen-averaged)	Papadakis et al. 1991 upper bound
Max abiotic CaCO ₃ via spontaneous urea hydrolysis	<0.001% (28d)	Krajewska 2018 ($t_{1/2} = 3.6$ yr)
Combined abiotic upper bound	<0.05%	Sum of above
	1.5-4.3%	This study, Fig. 5b
Ratio (measured/abiotic upper bound)	>30 (conservative) to >80 (central)	-

Fig. S1. Stress-strain curves of untreated and treated specimens (a) untreated soil, MICP-only treatment, and biochar-assisted MICP without CMC, (b) B5 series with varying CMC content, (c) candidate composite formulations at 1% CMC, and (d) selected formulation B5C1 at different initial Cd concentration.

Fig. S2. Representative post-UCS external appearances for (a) untreated soil, MICP-only treatment, and biochar-assisted MICP without CMC, and (b) B5 series with varying CMC content at initial Cd concentration of 1000 mg/kg.